

Proof of Goldbach’s Conjecture and Bertrand’s Postulate Using Prime Generator Theory (PGT)

Jabari Zakiya

Abstract: *Goldbach’s Conjecture* states every even integer $n > 2$ can be written as the sum of 2 primes, while *Bertrand’s Postulate* states for each $n \geq 2$ there is at least one prime p such that $n < p < 2n$. I show both are essentially statements on the primes distribution, and their inherent properties when modeled and understood as the residues of modular groups \mathbb{Z}_n . In addition, a much tighter dynamic bound on p than given by the *BP* will be presented.

Introduction

In 1742, the Prussian mathematician Christian Goldbach wrote a series of letters to the renowned Swiss mathematician Leonhard Euler, stating that every even number $n > 2$ can be written as the sum of prime numbers. In Goldbach’s time ‘1’ was considered a prime, so some of his conjectures varied between the sum of 2 or more primes when using it. Its modern statement is: **every even number > 2 can be written as the sum of 2 primes** (not necessarily unique). It’s been computer verified to hold for all even n up to 4×10^{18} [1].

In 1845, 23 year old French mathematician Joseph Bertrand stated: **for each $n \geq 2$, there is a prime p such that $n < p < 2n$** . Its 1852 proof made it a fundamental theorem of *Prime Number Theory*.

Prime Generator Theory (PGT) will be the basis of the mathematical framework used to formalize the properties of modular groups \mathbb{Z}_n over the even integers $n > 2$. I provide the minimum necessary axioms and properties here for the purpose of establishing the validity of the *GC*. More extensive expositions of the theory and applications of *PGT* can be found in my papers on the *Twin Primes Conjecture* [2], and my *Twin Primes Segmented Sieve* algorithm and code [3].

I show *Goldbach’s Conjecture (GC)* is really a (weak) statement about the inherent properties of primes when modeled and understood as the residues of modular groups \mathbb{Z}_n . I also show *Bertrand’s Postulate (BP)* falls directly out of it as a necessary (weaker) condition for the *GC* to be true. You can’t have the former without the later. I also present a much tighter, and dynamic, bound on p than given by the *BP*. But both are fundamentally statements on the distribution of the primes, *which do not exist randomly!*

The techniques used here will be “modern”, in the sense they don’t use or need the classical conceptual and numerical approaches used previously to prove the *BP*, and in the many unsuccessful attempts to prove the *GC*. Instead it will use the conceptual framework, logic, math and properties of the **residues of modular groups \mathbb{Z}_n** over the even integers $n > 2$. In fact, most of what needs to be understood is purely conceptual in nature, requiring very little number crunching. Finally, I present a simple algorithm to identify all the prime pairs for any n , its implementation in software, and empirical data.

Modular Group Residues

Prime Generator Theory is the understanding of prime numbers, their distribution, characteristics, gap structures, and other relationships, thru the properties of modular groups residues. For even values of n , it uses the **residues** of the modular groups \mathbb{Z}_n to construct **Prime Generators**, which efficiently generate every prime that is not a factor of n .

A modular group \mathbb{Z}_n is constructed from the integers $\{0 \dots n - 1\}$, with n the group's **modulus**. A **Prime Generator** is constructed from its **residues**, the r_i odd values coprime to n e.g. $\gcd(r_i, n) = 1$. Their r_i values are the: 1) coprime primes $p_j < n$, 2) their powers $p_j^e < n$, or 3) their cross-products $r_k = r_i \cdot r_j < n$. The number of r_i residues in \mathbb{Z}_n is an even value given by $\varphi(n)$, the **Euler Totient Function (ETF)**.

$$\varphi(n) = n \prod_{i=1}^j \frac{(p_i - 1)}{p_i} \quad (1)$$

The p_i are the j unique prime factors of n . Thus for $n = 12$: $\varphi(12) = 12 \frac{(2 - 1)}{2} \frac{(3 - 1)}{3} = 4$

We can easily identify the 4 residues with a **greatest common divisor (gcd)** of 1 in \mathbb{Z}_{12} , as: $\{1, 5, 7, 11\}$. Thus the **canonical residues** of \mathbb{Z}_n are '1' and the set of odd integer values $< n$ that are not multiples of its prime factors. Every prime coprime to n exists as a congruent modular value to a residue of \mathbb{Z}_n .

To identify the residues values of n we do not need to know its prime factors. We can simply do a $\gcd(r_i, n) = 1$ test on the odd integers in the half interval $[1, n/2)$ to identify its $\varphi(n)/2$ residue values. These are the **low-half-residues (lhr)** values. The $\varphi(n)/2$ **high-half-residues (hhr)** are then just their **modular complements**.

Modular Complement Properties

A very important property of modular residues is that they exist as **modular complement pairs (mcp)**. For a modulus n , each r_i residue has a modular complement r_i^c , adhering to these 2 modular properties:

$$r_i^c = n - r_i \quad (2)$$

$$r_i + r_i^c = n \quad (3)$$

Conceptually, a modular complement for an r_i is its **modular reflection** into its opposite half residues.

Looking at the residues $\{1, 5, 7, 11\}$ for \mathbb{Z}_{12} , when split into their $lhr||hhr$ values, and starting from the middle 6, we see $\{5, 7\}$ and $\{1, 11\}$ are its 2 mcp , which each sum to 12. **Thus to identify the $\varphi(n)$ residue values of n , we can just find the $\varphi(n)/2$ values $< n/2$, and their $n-r_i$ complements are the rest.**

Also, for every even modulus $n > 2$, the integers pair $\{1, n - 1\}$ are automatic mcp residues. For $n > 6$ the closest odd integers less|greater than the midpoint $n/2$ are also mcp residues. For \mathbb{Z}_{12} , $\{1, 11\}$ are mcp of the first type and $\{5, 7\}$ the latter. Thus we automatically know 4 residues, and 2 mcp , for $n > 6$.

Mirror Image Symmetry

An analog clock is the simplest form to show the modular complement properties of residues. For the group size \mathbb{Z}_{12} , we see the parallel horizontal lines connect pairs of hours on the left/right halves of the clock, and each pair sums to the group size 12. This is true for any even group size representation > 2 .

Figure 1.

Here the solid lines connect the two modular complement pair residues $\{1, 11\}$ and $\{5, 7\}$. As the prime factors of 12 are 2 and 3, the dashed lines connect their non-residue composite values, which occur as **modular composite factors pairs**. For $p = 2$, its composite complements must be a multiple of itself to have an even sum, but for $p = 3$ (or any odd prime factor), it must be an odd multiple of itself to have two odd numbers sum to an even n . Thus each r_i must have either an odd prime residue, a prime residue power, or an odd composite product of prime residues, as their modular complements.

For the *lhr* $\{1, 5\}$, $r_i \equiv r_i \pmod n$, but the *hhr* $\{7, 11\}$, can be thought of and used as, $n - r_i \equiv -r_i \pmod n$. We can thus write, use, and conceptually understand the *hhr* as the negative residue values of the *lhr*. Thus conceptually for the *lhr* values $0 < r_i < n/2$, their $-r_i$ equivalents are their **modular reflections** into their *hhr* complements $n/2 < -r_i < n$.

This is a modular arithmetic property analogous to the orientation of angles in trigonometry. Positive angles are defined as counter clockwise (CCW) around the clock, while clockwise (CW) angles are considered as negative. Here the CW residue values are considered positive, and the same units of values CCW around the clock can be referred to as negative values $\pmod n$. Thus if r_i CW units is a right side residue value, then the same units CCW on the left side are residue values too.

This creates a conceptually and arithmetically consistent structure for performing modular math. Thus for \mathbb{Z}_{12} , its *lhr* are $1 \equiv 1 \pmod{12}$ and $5 \equiv 5 \pmod{12}$, while the *hhr* are: $(12 - 1) = 11 \equiv -1 \pmod{12}$ and $(12 - 5) = 7 \equiv -5 \pmod{12}$. And as $n \equiv 0 \pmod n$, we have these conceptually simple relationships:

$$r_i^c = n - r_i \equiv -r_i \pmod n \quad (4)$$

$$r_i + r_i^c = r_i + -r_i = n \equiv 0 \pmod n \quad (5)$$

Figure 1. is a visual metaphor of the symmetry properties of every even \mathbb{Z}_n modular group. Thus we will see *Goldbach's Conjecture* can be restated and proven as the properties of the \mathbb{Z}_n residues and their modular complement pair relationships. Thus from the residue properties of even \mathbb{Z}_n modular groups, we will see there is at least one *mcp*, consisting of primes in each half, that sum to every even $n > 6$.

Definitions and Axioms

Here I define the terminology and establish the axiomatic mathematical foundation that will be used.

Definitions

Definition 1: A modular group \mathbb{Z}_n , with modulus n an even integer, is the set of integers $\{0..n - 1\}$.

Definition 2: A residue of \mathbb{Z}_n is an integer $r_i < n$ coprime to n , i.e. an integer $r_i < n$ e.g. $\gcd(r_i, n) = 1$.

Definition 3: A modular complement (mc) of an r_i , i.e. r_i^c , is the residue value r_j e.g. $r_j = r_i^c = n - r_i$.

Definition 4: A modular complement pair (mcp) of \mathbb{Z}_n are two residues that sum to n .

Definition 5: A prime complement pair (pcp) of \mathbb{Z}_n is a modular complement pair of two primes.

Definition 6: A trivial prime pair (tpp) is a single prime added to itself, e.g. $n = 2p = p + p$.

Definition 7: The low-half-residues (lhr) are the set of residues in the interval $0 < \{r_{lo}\} < n/2$.

Definition 8: The high-half-residues (hhr) are the set of residues in the interval $n/2 < \{r_{hi}\} < n$.

Axioms

Axiom 1: The number of residues of \mathbb{Z}_n is determined by $\varphi(n)$, the Euler Totient Function (ETF).

Axiom 2: The number of residues is even, as each odd prime factor p_i of n contributes $(p_i - 1)$ to $\varphi(n)$.

Axiom 3: The set of the $\varphi(n)$ residue values $\{r_i\}$ consists of the odd values in $\{1..n - 1\}$ coprime to n .

Axiom 4: The set of $\{r_i\}$ residues contain all the coprime primes $< n$.

Axiom 5: The powers of a residue $r_i < n$, i.e. its $r_i^e < n$, are also residues, as they too are coprime to n .

Axiom 6: The products $< n$ of two residues is also a residue, i.e. $r_k = r_i \cdot r_j < n$ is also coprime to n .

Axiom 7: The two residues of an mcp|pcp consist of an $r_i < n/2$ and its complement $r_i^c = n - r_i > n/2$.

Axiom 8: Each residue can only be the modular complement to one residue in its opposite half.

Axiom 9: There are $\varphi(n)/2$ modular complement pairs for each \mathbb{Z}_n modular group.

Goldbach's Conjecture can be restated within the framework of Prime Generator Theory (PGT) as:
every even integer $n > 6$ has for its modular group \mathbb{Z}_n at least one prime complement pair (pcp).

Integers 4 and 6 have form $n = 2p$, and thus single trivial prime pairs, $4 = 2 + 2$ and $6 = 3 + 3$, to satisfy the general GC for $n > 2$. Every other integer of form $n = 2p$ (of the infinitely many) have a similar tpp, in addition to at least one pcp. The proof, algorithm, code, and data presented herein ignores them.

PGT Proof of Goldbach's Conjecture

A minimal proof need only show there is at least one *pcp* prime pair that sums to n for all even $n > 6$. This will be established using the residue mirror symmetry|reflection properties of modular groups \mathbb{Z}_n . It will be proved, a simply crafted bounded *hhr* region close to n always contains at least one prime p_q , the modular complement to a small *lhr* prime $p_m = n - p_q$, forming a $\{p_m, p_q\}$ *pcp* prime pair, as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Residue Properties

Lemma 1. For residues $r_i < n/2$, their modular complements $n - r_i$ cannot be multiples of themselves.

Proof: Assume $n - r_i = k \cdot r_i$. Then $k = (n - r_i)/r_i = n/r_i - 1$, requiring n/r_i be an even integer, and r_i a factor of n . But r_i is coprime to n , and thus cannot be a factor of n , thus this is a contradiction.

Therefore the modular complements $n - r_i$ for the residues $r_i < n/2$ cannot be multiples of themselves.

Lemma 2. For residues $r_i < n/2$, their modular complements $n - r_i$ cannot be powers of themselves.

Proof: Assume $n - r_i = r_i^e$. Thus $n = r_i^e + r_i = r_i(r_i^{e-1} + 1)$, giving $n/r_i = (r_i^{e-1} + 1)$ for $e \geq 2$. Then n/r_i must be an integer, requiring r_i be a factor of n . But r_i is coprime to n , thus this is a contradiction.

Therefore the modular complements $n - r_i$ for the residues $r_i < n/2$ cannot be powers of themselves.

Corollary 1.

For the $\varphi(n)/2$ *lhr* $r_i < n/2$, their *hhr* modular complements $n - r_i$ can only be either:

1) a prime p_r , 2) a prime power p_r^e , or 3) the cross-product $r_j \cdot r_k$ of residues not including themselves.

Define $r_0 = 1$ as the first canonical residue of n .

Define $r_1 = p_i$ as the first|smallest prime not a factor of n .

Lemma 3. The set of residues $\{r_i\} < r_i^2$, i.e. in $r_1 \leq \{r_i\} < r_1^2$, are the coprime primes $< r_1^2$.

Proof: As r_1 is the first prime residue, r_1^2 is the first multiple of any residue in \mathbb{Z}_n .

Thus, every residue in $1 < r_k < r_1^2$ cannot be a multiple of r_1 , or any other residue, thus is a prime $< r_1^2$.

If $r_1 = 3$, then $\{5, 7\} < 9$ are the next ordered residues if not factors of n . If $\{5, 7\}$ are factors, the next residue is $r_2 = r_1^2 = 9$ if $< n$, because 11 is the next larger prime. In this case, if $r_3 = 11$, then all the coprime primes residues $\{r_i\} < (r_3^2 = 121)$ are also primes $< n$. And we continue in this manner.

We can extend this for all $r_m < n/2$, to establish all the coprime prime $p_r \leq \{p_m\} < p_r^2$ are residues to n . The residues also contain all the powers of the prime residues p_r e.g. $\{p_r, p_r^2, \dots\} < n$, in addition to the residue cross-products $r_j \cdot r_k < n$. However, once for some r_n (*n*th residue), $r_n^2 > n$, no larger *lhr* r_{n+1} prime power, or cross-product, can be a residue $< n$. Then for r_{n-1} (previous residue), r_{n-1}^2 is the largest square that can be a *hhr* $< n$. Let's designate this residue as: $r_{max} = r_{n-1}$ for some *lhr* $r_i < n/2$.

Thus the *hhr* in $r_{max}^2 < \{p_r || r_{cp}\} < n$ can only be p_r primes or cross-products of the type $r_{cp} = r_{max-} \cdot r_{max+}$, with $r_{max-} \leq r_{max}$ and $r_{max+} > r_{max}$. Thus no larger *lhr* power can be a residue e.g. $r_{max}^2 < r_i^e < n$, for $e \geq 2$.

When n is small, only primes exist in the region. As n increases, cross-products, and more primes, will populate it, as a function of the prime factorization of n . When the cross-products and prime powers are filtered out, only the primes in both halves are left, and form the *pcp* prime pairs for even $n > 6$.

Optimum Bounded Regions

The optimum bounded *hhr* region that contains prime residues that always form at least one *pcp* is:

$$r_{max}^2 < \{p_r\} < n \quad (6)$$

It **dynamically adjusts** to create the smallest bounded *hhr* region of *pcp* primes, and has generic form:

$$\text{LowBound} < \{p_i\} < \text{HighBound} \quad (7)$$

High Bound Limit

Normally the *hhr* high bound is just n . But we want the smallest region a prime *hhr* can exist within.

Because $n - 1$ is the modular complement for $r_0 = 1$, whether its prime or not, it cannot be part of a *pcp*. We thus set the *hhr* high bound to $n - 2$, the next smaller even value from n . Thus any *hhr* $r_i < n - 2$ can possibly be a prime *hhr* that can form a *pcp* with a small *lhr* prime.

Low Bound Limit

From the low bound of (6), the largest *lhr* value whose square satisfies $r_{max}^2 < n - 2$, is given by:

$$r_{max} = \text{isqrt}(n - 2) \quad (8)$$

where $\text{isqrt}(x)$ is the integer square root of x . Ex: $\text{isqrt}(8) = 2$, $\text{isqrt}(9) = 3$, $\text{isqrt}(15) = 3$, $\text{isqrt}(16) = 4$.

Applying Modular Reflection

We now know that r_{max} sets the limit as to how large a *lhr* can be; an odd *lhr* value e.g. $r_i \leq r_{max} < n/2$. Because r_{max} is computed 2 *hhr* units below n , its *lhr* region high bound reflection must do so too:

$$\text{HighBound}_{lhr} = r_{max} + 2 \quad (9)$$

We now determine its *hhr* modular (negative) reflection. Starting at the top of the Figure 1. clock, the equivalent region extends down r_{max} CCW units. Again, because we computed the value from $n - 2$, and not n , the *hhr* region extends r_{max} units below it. Thus the *hhr* region low bound is:

$$\text{LowBound}_{hhr} = (n - 2) - r_{max} \quad (10)$$

Thus the smallest bounded *hhr* region which a prime residue exists within whose *lhr mc* forms a *pcp* is:

$$(n - 2) - r_{max} \leq p_r < n - 2 \quad (11)$$

We use $\leq p_r$ vs $< p_r$ because LowBound can be an odd|prime value, while odd $p_r < n - 2$ is always true. The equivalent *lhr* bounded region is then:

$$2 < p_r \leq r_{max} + 2 \quad (12)$$

We use $p_r \leq r_{max}$ vs $p_r < r_{max}$ here too, as r_{max} can be odd, making the right side odd.

These bounded regions always produce a *pcp* for increasing n . And as n increases, and its factorization includes more and larger primes, other *pcp* prime pairs will be created, whose total will greatly exceed those coming from them alone. However, the analysis of these regions alone proves the *GC's* validity. In fact, these optimally adjusting dynamic bounds have implications far beyond *Goldbach's Conjecture*.

Bounded Bonding of Primes

Shown again are the parameters of the *lhr* and *hhr* bounded regions that produce at least one *pcp*.

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 r_{max} & hhr \text{ bounds} & lhr \text{ bounds} \\
 isqrt(n-2) & (n-2) - r_{max} \leq p_r < n-2 & 2 < p_r \leq r_{max} + 2
 \end{array} \quad (13)$$

The modular complement and symmetry relationships between the residues are inherent and immutable properties of \mathbb{Z}_n modular groups. These properties define the distribution of the residues, which means they define the distribution of the primes, whose values and relationships constitute them.

Let's start with the integers 4 and 6. They have $\phi(2|4) = 2$ residues, $\{1, 3\}$ and $\{1, 5\}$, which are their single *mcp*. In Goldbach's time they would have been considered a prime pair by some.

For $8 = 2^3$, its residues include all the coprime primes < 8 , $\{1, 3, 5, 7\}$, whose *mcp* are: $\{1, 7\}$, $\{3, 5\}$. Here $r_{max} = 2$, giving the bounded regions $4 \leq 5 < 6$ and $2 < 3 \leq 4$. For 10 it's, $6 \leq 7 < 8$ and $2 < 3 \leq 4$. And we see the bounds dynamically adjusting to give the smallest possible regions the *pcp* exist within.

The residues for $10 = 2 \cdot 5$ are $\{1, 3, 7, 9\}$, with *mcp* $\{1, 9 = 3^2\}$. But unlike for 4, 6, and 8, it wouldn't have been considered a prime pair even in Goldbach's time. But this explicitly illustrates why we set the *hhr* upper limit to $n - 2$ and not n . Integers 8, 10, 12, 14, and 38 are the only ones with one *pcp*.

Metaphorically, to understand the primes we must understand there is a clear deterministic chemistry that exists within the residue properties of modular groups that defines their behavior. Part of that chemistry tells us the primes bond in pairs, and with other relationships, that are built into the structure of modular groups. (For example, verification of *Polignac's Twin Primes* conjectures [2]).

The primes, as the primary residues of modular groups, are their fundamental building block elements. And their powers and cross-products are their molecules. And like with the chemical elements, there are defined ways we know they can and must move and interact, and ways they can't.

The *pcp* are the symmetric load bearing beams of the structure of these modular groups. They are the bonding forces that hold everything together. It is part of the chemistry of the primes that they bond in this manner. As n grows so do the *pcp*, in a structured way that is a function of the factorization of n .

We can conceptually determine the number of *pcp* bounded by r_{max} from the following formula:

$$\#pcp(r_{max}) = \#lhr(r_{max}) - \#hhr(r_{max})_{r_{cp}} - \#lhr(r_{max})_{r_{cp}} || p_r^e \quad (14)$$

However, the actual algorithm to determine the number and values of the *pcp*, within the r_{max} bounded regions and for all n , is quite simple and short, easy to do by hand, and translates easily into software.

Again, the ability to determine the number and values of the *pcp*, and to create optimum dynamically adjusting boundary conditions, is based on the understanding of the properties of how the primes exist as the residues of these simple \mathbb{Z}_n modular groups. Thus the *GC* is really a (weak) statement on the distribution of the primes, whose structure requires they bond in the group patterns the *GC* proposed.

We will also see *Bertrand's Postulate* is another (weaker) statement on the distribution of the primes.

PGT's Postulate

Bertrand's Postulate (BP) states: **for each $n \geq 2$, there is a prime p such that $n < p < 2n$.** From the perspective of *PGT*, this is merely saying there is always at least one prime residue within the *hhr* for n . We know this to be trivially true, because you can't have no prime residues in either the *lhr* or *hhr*.

PGT's Postulate (PGTP) states: **for each $n \geq 2$, there is a prime p such that $2n - (2n)^{1/2} \leq p < 2n$.** We can equivalently simplify it: **for each even $n > 2$, there is a prime p such that $n - n^{1/2} \leq p < n$.**

For a *prime complement pairs (pcp)* to exist their must be a prime p_i e.g. $2 < p_i < n/2$ and another p_j e.g. $n/2 < p_j < n$. The later requirement is just a restatement of the *BP* that $n < p < 2n, n \geq 2$. We previously established the optimum low bounds to identify at least one *pcp* prime within $\text{LowBound} \leq p < n$ to be:

$$\text{LowBound}_{(n-2)} = (n - 2) - \text{isqrt}(n - 2) \tag{15}$$

Using the stricter *PGTP* bound, to mimic the *BP*, will identify at least one prime, not necessarily a *pcp*.

$$\text{LowBound}_{(n)} = n - \text{isqrt}(n) \tag{16}$$

Let's compare the two bounds for the first few even values of n , and the *pcp* prime pairs identified.

n	$\text{LowBound}_{(n)} \leq p < n$	PCP Prime Pairs	$\text{LowBound}_{(n-2)} \leq p < n-2$
6	$4 \leq p < 6 : p = 5$	{3, 3}*	$2 \leq p < 4 : p = 3$
8	$6 \leq p < 8 : p = 7$	{3, 5}	$4 \leq p < 6 : p = 5$
10	$7 \leq p < 10 : p = 7$	{3, 7}	$6 \leq p < 8 : p = 7$
12	$9 \leq p < 12 : p = 11$	{5, 7}	$7 \leq p < 10 : p = 7$
14	$11 \leq p < 14 : p = \{11, 13\}$	{3, 11}	$9 \leq p < 12 : p = 11$
16	$12 \leq p < 16 : p = 13$	{5, 11}, {3, 13}	$11 \leq p < 14 : p = \{11, 13\}$
18	$14 \leq p < 18 : p = 17$	{5, 13}	$12 \leq p < 16 : p = 13$
20	$16 \leq p < 20 : p = \{17, 19\}$	{3, 17}	$14 \leq p < 18 : p = 17$
22	$18 \leq p < 22 : p = 19$	{5, 17}, {3, 19}	$16 \leq p < 20 : p = \{17, 19\}$
24	$20 \leq p < 24 : p = 23$	{5, 19}	$18 \leq p < 22 : p = 19$
26	$21 \leq p < 26 : p = 23$	{3, 23}	$20 \leq p < 24 : p = 23$
28	$23 \leq p < 28 : p = 23$	{5, 23}	$21 \leq p < 26 : p = 23$
30	$25 \leq p < 30 : p = 29$	{7, 23}	$23 \leq p < 28 : p = 23$
32	$27 \leq p < 32 : p = \{29, 31\}$	{3, 29}	$25 \leq p < 30 : p = 29$
34	$29 \leq p < 34 : p = \{29, 31\}$	{5, 29}, {3, 31}	$27 \leq p < 32 : p = \{29, 31\}$
36	$30 \leq p < 36 : p = 31$	{7, 29}, {5, 31}	$29 \leq p < 34 : p = \{29, 31\}$
38	$32 \leq p < 38 : p = 37$	{7, 31}	$30 \leq p < 36 : p = 31$
40	$34 \leq p < 40 : p = 37$	{3, 37}	$32 \leq p < 38 : p = 37$
42	$36 \leq p < 42 : p = \{37, 41\}$	{5, 37}	$34 \leq p < 40 : p = 37$
44	$38 \leq p < 44 : p = \{41, 43\}$	{7, 37}, {3, 41}	$36 \leq p < 42 : p = \{37, 41\}$
46	$40 \leq p < 46 : p = \{41, 43\}$	{5, 41}, {3, 43}	$38 \leq p < 44 : p = \{41, 43\}$
48	$42 \leq p < 48 : p = \{43, 47\}$	{7, 41}, {5, 43}	$40 \leq p < 46 : p = \{41, 43\}$
50	$43 \leq p < 50 : p = \{43, 47\}$	{7, 43}, {3, 47}	$42 \leq p < 48 : p = \{43, 47\}$

As n increases, the lower bounds dynamically grow, creating much tighter bounds on p than the *BP*.

100	$90 \leq p < 100 : p = 97$	{11, 89}, {3, 97}	$89 \leq p < 98 : p = \{89, 97\}$
256	$240 \leq p < 256 : p = \{241, 151\}$	{17, 239}, {5, 251}	$239 \leq p < 254 : p = \{239, 241, 251\}$

For 256, the bounded primes are {239, 241, 251}, and cross-products {243, 245, 247, 249, 253}. The *mc* for 241 is $15 = 3 \cdot 5$, but 5 forms the *pcp* with 251. The *mc* for 3 is $253 = 11 \cdot 23$, *mc* to 245 and 233, and the *mc* for 247 is $9 = 3^2$. Now $243 = 3^5$, but $3|3^2 < (r_{max}=15)$, and $3^3|3^4$ are residues too, so 243 really is $3 \cdot 81$ and $9 \cdot 27$. For $245 = 5 \cdot 7^2$, then $5|7 < r_{max}$ multiply residues $49|35$, and $249 = 3 \cdot 83$, a product of primes. Also, 256 has 6 other *pcp* below this region. In comparison, the *BP* bound is: $128 < p < 256$.

Thus the *BP* structurally falls out of the *GC*, as its necessarily true for the *GC* to be true. But the *GC* doesn't need it, as seen here, as much tighter bounds on p can be created using the various properties of modular groups. The *BP* is a mere consequence of the *GC* being true, and states a weaker bound on p .

In essence (15) and (16) are numerically the same bounds, as they both apply numerically to just even values. But as shown in the construction of their derivations, *they have different conceptual meanings* and purposes, which must be understood to know when to apply them, and what they tell you.

PGT's Postulate Empirical Verification

Shown is Crystal code to verify *PGT's Postulate*. It first computes the strict **low_bnd** for n . If **low_bnd** is prime n passes. If not prime, it computes the first prime greater than it, and if $< n$ (inside the bound) it passes. The code is fast and memory efficient, and does the minimum amount of required work. It uses two fast custom methods **prime?** and **next_prime**, to perform the necessary primality tests shown.

Empirical results establish, only $n = 126$ fails the strict **low_bnd**, but it passes (with all other values) for **low_bnd-2**. For 126 the strict bounds are: $115 \leq p < 126$. Lowering it by 2 to $113 \leq p < 126$ catches the prime $p = 113$. But as we're concerned with the *asymptotic behavior of n* as it becomes large ($n \rightarrow \infty$), the strict **low_bnd** accurately characterizes the distribution of the primes, and is a much more precise statement of it than *Bertrand's Postulate*.

At the time of writing, *PGT's Postulate* was verified for every n up to 10^{12} (1,000,000,000,000). It was also verified for at least the first 100B (100,000,000,000) starting at $10^{13}..10^{19}$, to cover as much of the 64-bit ($2^{64} = 18,446,744,073,709,551,616$) number space as possible. Hopefully others will extend the number space that is tested.

```
# Compile: $ crystal build --release --mcpu native pgt_postulate_check.cr
# Run as:  $ ./pgt_postulate_check 10_000_000_000 20_000_000_000

require "./prime-utils.cr"           # provides methods: prime? | next_prime

def pgt_postulate_checks(n1, n2)     # check at least one prime in bounded region for n
  n1.step(to: n2, by: 2).each do |n| # check for each even number n in range
    low_bnd = (n - Math.isqrt(n)) | 1 # make value next odd number if even
    puts "no prime in bound for #{n.format}" unless low_bnd.prime? || low_bnd.next_prime < n
    print "\rchecked up to #{n.format}" if n.divisible_by?(1_000_000) # output for every 1M done
  end
  puts "\nTested Values #{n1.format} to #{n2.format}"
end

n1 = (ARGV[0].to_u64 underscore: true) # inputs taken as u64 values up to 1.8 x 10^19 (2^64)
n2 = (ARGV[1].to_u64 underscore: true) # change to u128 for values up to 3.4 x 10^38 (2^128)

t1 = Time.monotonic                  # start execution timing
pgt_postulate_checks(n1, n2)         # execute code
pp Time.monotonic - t1               # show execution time
```

```
$ ./pgt_postulate_check 4 500_000_000      $ ./pgt_postulate_check 500_000_000 1_000_000_000
no prime in bound for 126                  checked up to 1,000,000,000
checked up to 500,000,000                  Tested Values 500,000,000 to 1,000,000,000
Tested Values 4 to 500,000,000             00:02:40.765757603
00:02:17.650365026
```

Prime Pairs Algorithm

An algorithm to identify all the *pcp* prime pairs is very short and simple, which is demonstrated here. It merely removes (filters out) the composite *non-pcp* residues, leaving only the prime residues of *pcp*.

1) For even n treat as Z_n , and identify its **low-half-residues (lhr)** $< n/2$. The residue values r are odd integers **coprime** to n , e.g. $\text{gcd}(r, n) = 1$. The **1st canonical residue** is 1, but 1 is not prime, so it can't be part of a prime pair, so test the odds numbers from $3 < n/2$ to identify the **pcp lhr**.

2) Store in **lhr_mults** the powers of r_i in **lhr** $< n-2$; these are composite residues. We test up to $n-2$ because $n-1$ is the **mcp** for 1, which can't be part of a **pcp**. Once the square of an r_i (i.e. r_i^2) $> n-2$, exit process, as all other r_j are $> n-2$.

3) Store in **lhr_mults** the cross-products $r_i * r_j < n-2$. Starting with smallest r_i **lhr**, test cross-products with all larger **lhr**. If $r_i > \sqrt{n-2}$, exit process, as r_i^2 , and all other r_i **lhr** cross-products, are $> n-2$. If for next larger residue r_j , $r_i * r_j > n-2$, exit process, as no others are $< n-2$. Otherwise save in **lhr_mults** cross-product $r_i * r_j < n-2$, repeat for the next larger r_j **lhr**.

lhr_mults now has all the non-prime composite residue values $< n-2$.

4) Remove from the **lhr** the **non-pcp lhr_mults** values. The **pcp** prime pairs remain.
 a) For **lhr_mults** values $r > n/2$, convert to their **mcp** values $n-r$.
 b) All now are **non-pcp** values $< n/2$; remove their values from **lhr** list.

The **lhr** list now contains all prime residues whose **mcp** make a **pcp** prime pair. For the remaining primes p_n , the **pcp** for n are the prime pairs $[p_n, n - p_n]$.

Let's now do a non-trivial example that performs all the algorithmic parts.

Example: Find the **pcp** prime pairs for $n = 50 = 2 * 5 * 5$.

1) Identify the **lhr** values $< n/2$.

Write out list of odd numbers from 3 to $< 25 = 50/2$

[3 5 7 9 11 13 15 17 19 21 23]

The **lhr** are values r coprime (share no factors) to n ; i.e. $\text{gcd}(r, 50) = 1$.

[3 7 9 11 13 17 19 21 23]

Thus: **lhr** = [3, 7, 9, 11, 13, 17, 19, 21, 23]

2) Store in **lhr_mults** the powers of the **lhr** $< 48 = 50-2$.

a) for 3: **lhr_mults** = []
 3 * 3: **lhr_mults** = [9], as 9 < 48
 3 * 9: **lhr_mults** = [9, 27], as 27 < 48
 3 * 27: stop powers for 3, as 81 > 48
 b) for 7: exit powers process; as 7 * 7 = 49 > 48; no other **lhr** power can be < 48.

3) Store in **lhr_mults** the **lhr** cross-products < 48.

a) for 3: **lhr_mults** = [9, 27]
 3 * 7: **lhr_mults** = [9, 27, 21], as 21 < 48
 3 * 9: **lhr_mults** = [9, 27, 21, 27], as 27 < 48
 3 * 11: **lhr_mults** = [9, 27, 21, 27, 33], as 33 < 48
 3 * 13: **lhr_mults** = [9, 27, 21, 27, 33, 39], as 39 < 48
 3 * 17: stop cross-products process for 3, as 3 * 17 = 51 > 48

b) for 7: $lhr_mults = [9, 27, 21, 27, 33, 39]$
 $7 * 9$: exit total cross-product process, as $7 * 9 = 63 > 48$;

4) Remove from the **lhr** the **lhr_mults** values

$lhr = [3, 7, 9, 11, 13, 17, 19, 21, 23]$

$lhr_mults = [9, 27, 21, 27, 33, 39]$

a) Convert **lhr_mults** values $> 25 = 50/2$ to their modular complement value $50-r$

$lhr_mults = [9, 23, 21, 23, 17, 11]$

b) Remove from **lhr** values in **lhr_mults**

$lhr = [3, 7, 9, 11, 13, 17, 19, 21, 23]$

$lhr_mults = [9, 23, 21, 23, 17, 11]$

b1) For **lhr_mults** val 9; remove from **lhr**:

$lhr_mults = [9, \overset{\wedge}{23}, 21, 23, 17, 11]$

$lhr = [3, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 21, 23]$

b2) For **lhr_mults** val 23; remove from **lhr**:

$lhr_mults = [9, 23, \overset{\wedge}{21}, 23, 17, 11]$

$lhr = [3, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 21]$

b3) For **lhr_mults** val 21; remove from **lhr**:

$lhr_mults = [9, 23, 21, \overset{\wedge}{23}, 17, 11]$

$lhr = [3, 7, 11, 13, 19]$

b4) For **lhr_mults** val 17; remove from **lhr**:

$lhr_mults = [9, 23, 21, 23, 17, \overset{\wedge}{11}]$

$lhr = [3, 7, 11, 13, 19]$

b5) For **lhr_mults** val 11; remove from **lhr**:

$lhr_mults = [9, 23, 21, 23, 17, \overset{\wedge}{11}]$

$lhr = [3, 7, 13, 19]$

lhr list of only primes now exists; as original **lhr** composite residues have been removed.

Thus **lhr** = **[3, 7, 13, 19]** now contains 4 prime **pcp** residues for $n = 50$.

Their 4 **pcp** prime pairs values for 50 are:

pcp for 3: $[3, 50 - 3] = [3, 47]$

pcp for 7: $[7, 50 - 7] = [7, 43]$

pcp for 13: $[13, 50 - 13] = [13, 37]$

pcp for 19: $[19, 50 - 19] = [19, 31]$

Every even integer $n > 6$ has at least one **pcp** prime pair.

This is a property of **modular groups Z_n** over even integers n .

Prime Pairs Code

Here is a Crystal implementation of the simplified canonical prime pairs algorithm that was given. It simplifies having to find the prime powers into just finding their squares. Higher residue powers are then cross-products of their different residue powers values. It also eliminates the `lhr_mults` array by first converting cross-product values $> n/2$ into their `lhr_mc` values and storing them into `lhr_del`.

```
def prime_pairs_lohi(n) # generate the pcp prime pairs for even n > 6
  return puts "Input not even n > 2" unless n.even? && n > 6

  # generate the low-half-residues (lhr) r < n/2
  lhr = 3u64.step(to: n//2, by: 2).select { |r| r if r.gcd(n) == 1 }.to_a
  ndiv2, rhi = n//2, n-2 # lhr:hhr midpoint, max residue limit

  # identify and store all powers and cross-products of the lhr members < n-2
  lhr_del = [] of typeof(n) # lhr multiples, not part of a pcp
  lhr_dup = lhr.dup # make copy of the lhr members list
  while (r = lhr_dup.shift) && !lhr_dup.empty? # do mults of current r w/others
    rmax = rhi // r # r can't multiply others with greater vals
    lhr_del << (r*r < ndiv2 ? r*r : n - r*r) if r < rmax # for r^2 multiples
    break if lhr_dup[0] > rmax # exit if product of consecutive r's > n-2
    lhr_dup.each do |ri| # for each residue in reduced list
      break if ri > rmax # exit for r if cross-product with ri > n-2
      lhr_del << (r*ri < ndiv2 ? r*ri : n - r*ri) # store value if < n-2
    end # check cross-products of next lhr member
  end

  lhr -= lhr_del # remove from lhr its lhr_mults, pcp remain
  pp [n, lhr.size] # show n and pcp prime pairs count
  pp [lhr.first, n-lhr.first] # show first pcp prime pair of n
  pp [lhr.last, n-lhr.last] # show last pcp prime pair of n
end

n = (ARGV[0].to_u64 underscore: true) # get n input from terminal
t1 = Time.monotonic # start execution timing
prime_pairs_lohi(n) # execute code
pp Time.monotonic - t1 # show execution time
```

This is a faster, memory efficient version, which directly identifies the *pcp*; timing differences shown.

```
require "./prime-utils.cr" # provides methods: prime? | next_prime

def prime_pairs_lohi(n) # generate the pcp prime pairs for even n > 6
  return puts "Input not even n > 2" unless n.even? && n > 6

  p, pcp = 2u64, [] of typeof(n) # identify/store the lhr pcp primes
  while (p = p.next_prime) < n//2; pcp << p if (n - p).prime? end

  pp [n, pcp.size] # show n and pcp prime pairs count
  pp [pcp.first, n-pcp.first] # show first pcp prime pair of n
  pp [pcp.last, n-pcp.last] # show last pcp prime pair of n
end

n = (ARGV[0].to_u64 underscore: true) # get n input from terminal
t1 = Time.monotonic # start execution timing
prime_pairs_lohi(n) # execute code
pp Time.monotonic - t1 # show execution time
```

```
$ ./primes_pairs_lohi 12_345_678 $ ./primes_pairs_lohi 123_456_780
[12345678, 71169] [123456780, 717906]
[31, 12345647] [19, 123456761]
[6172799, 6172879] [61728367, 61728413]
00:00:00.674223922 | 00:00:00.219135707 00:00:05.727994126 | 00:00:02.504820498
```

Empirical Data Table 1.

The data shown here is: # residues < $n/2$, primes cnt < $n/2|n$, $pcps$, $pcps$ % of primes, and 1st|last $pcps$.

n	$\varphi(n)/2$	$\pi(n/2)$	$\pi(n)$	PCP	% PCP($n/2 n$)		First Prime Pair	Last Prime Pair
1,000,000	200,000	41,538	78,498	5,402	13.00	13.76	[17, 999983]	[499943, 500057]
2,000,000	400,000	78,498	148,933	9,720	12.38	13.05	[7, 1999993]	[999961, 1000039]
3,000,000	400,000	114,155	216,816	27,502	24.09	25.37	[43, 2999957]	[1499857, 1500143]
4,000,000	800,000	148,933	283,146	17,630	11.84	12.45	[29, 3999971]	[1999853, 2000147]
5,000,000	1,000,000	183,072	348,513	21,290	11.63	12.22	[37, 4999963]	[2499949, 2500051]
6,000,000	800,000	216,816	412,849	49,783	22.96	24.12	[7, 5999993]	[2999911, 3000089]
7,000,000	1,200,000	250,150	476,648	34,284	13.71	14.39	[3, 6999997]	[3499967, 3500033]
8,000,000	1,600,000	283,146	539,777	31,753	11.21	11.77	[7, 7999993]	[3999763, 4000237]
9,000,000	1,200,000	315,948	602,489	70,619	22.35	23.44	[7, 8999993]	[4499953, 4500047]
10,000,000	2,000,000	348,513	664,579	38,807	11.14	11.68	[29, 9999971]	[4999913, 5000087]
11,000,000	2,000,000	380,800	726,517	46,812	12.29	12.89	[3, 10999997]	[5499979, 5500021]
12,000,000	1,600,000	412,849	788,060	90,877	22.01	23.06	[11, 11999989]	[5999947, 6000053]
13,000,000	2,400,000	444,757	849,252	53,398	12.01	12.58	[3, 12999997]	[6499841, 6500159]
14,000,000	2,400,000	476,648	910,077	62,026	13.01	13.63	[19, 13999981]	[6999997, 7000003]
15,000,000	2,000,000	508,261	970,704	110,140	21.67	22.69	[19, 14999981]	[7499939, 7500061]
16,000,000	3,200,000	539,777	1,031,130	58,383	10.82	11.32	[11, 15999989]	[7999913, 8000087]
17,000,000	3,200,000	571,119	1,091,314	65,592	11.48	12.02	[37, 16999963]	[8499979, 8500021]
18,000,000	2,400,000	602,489	1,151,367	129,501	21.49	22.49	[13, 17999987]	[8999777, 9000223]
19,000,000	3,600,000	633,578	1,211,050	71,656	11.31	11.83	[3, 18999997]	[9499811, 9500189]
20,000,000	4,000,000	664,579	1,270,607	70,730	10.64	11.13	[19, 19999981]	[9999739, 10000261]
21,000,000	2,400,000	695,609	1,329,943	177,440	25.51	26.68	[23, 20999977]	[10499963, 10500037]
22,000,000	4,000,000	726,517	1,389,261	85,476	11.77	12.31	[23, 21999977]	[10999811, 11000189]
23,000,000	4,400,000	757,288	1,448,221	83,727	11.06	11.56	[7, 22999993]	[11499949, 11500051]
24,000,000	3,200,000	788,060	1,507,122	165,922	21.05	22.02	[19, 23999981]	[11999927, 12000073]
25,000,000	5,000,000	818,703	1,565,927	85,838	10.48	10.96	[17, 24999983]	[12499481, 12500519]
26,000,000	4,800,000	849,252	1,624,527	97,209	11.45	11.97	[67, 25999933]	[12999919, 13000081]
27,000,000	3,600,000	879,640	1,683,065	184,050	20.92	21.87	[19, 26999981]	[13499939, 13500061]
28,000,000	4,800,000	910,077	1,741,430	113,922	12.52	13.08	[101, 27999899]	[13999691, 14000309]
29,000,000	5,600,000	940,455	1,799,676	101,387	10.78	11.27	[61, 28999939]	[14499973, 14500027]
30,000,000	4,000,000	970,704	1,857,859	202,166	20.83	21.76	[11, 29999989]	[14999969, 15000031]
31,000,000	6,000,000	1,000,862	1,915,979	107,710	10.76	11.24	[11, 30999989]	[15499943, 15500057]
32,000,000	6,400,000	1,031,130	1,973,815	106,627	10.34	10.80	[61, 31999939]	[15999871, 16000129]
33,000,000	4,000,000	1,061,198	2,031,667	243,780	22.97	23.99	[17, 32999983]	[16499939, 16500061]
34,000,000	6,400,000	1,091,314	2,089,379	120,272	11.02	11.51	[107, 33999893]	[16999859, 17000141]
35,000,000	6,000,000	1,121,389	2,146,775	138,452	12.35	12.89	[31, 34999969]	[17499793, 17500207]

Table 1.

The Tale of Table 1.

The variance seen in the *pcp* numbers is due to the number and characteristics of the residues $\varphi(n)$, which is due to the number, size, and values of the prime factors for each n , as shown here.

```

$ ./prime_pairs_lohi 148_000_006           $ ./prime_pairs_lohi 150_000_006
[1480000006, 436612]                       [1500000006, 708844]
[3, 1480000003]                             [5, 1500000001]
[73999643, 74000363]                       [74999959, 75000047]
00:00:14.870575626                          00:00:09.438616531
    
```

While close in size, 148,000,006 has substantially fewer *pcp*, and takes more time to process them. That's because its residues produce more prime powers and cross-products that have to be filtered out. And that's due to the difference in their prime factors, which determine their \mathbb{Z}_n groups residue values.

```

148_000_006.factors                          150_000_006.factors
[[2, 1], [7, 1], [11, 1], [19, 1], [50581, 1]]  [[2, 1], [3, 1], [13, 2], [29, 1], [5101, 1]]
φ(148,000,006) = (2 - 1) (7 - 1) (11 - 1) (19 - 1) (50581 - 1) = 54,626,400
φ(150,000,006) = 13 (2 - 1) (3 - 1) (13 - 1) (29 - 1) (5101 - 1) = 44,553,600
    
```

So n values with relatively larger *pcp* counts have fewer residues, with relatively larger values. They produce relatively fewer prime factors and cross-products, leaving more *lhr* primes to form *pcp* with.

However, the much more interesting phenomena is what the data reveals in the two % PCP columns. These are the percentages of all the primes $\pi(n)$ less than n , and in low half $\pi(n/2)$, that form the *pcp*.

$$\% \text{PCP}(n/2) = (pcp / \pi(n/2)) \cdot 100 \qquad \% \text{PCP}(n) = (2 \cdot pcp / \pi(n)) \cdot 100 \qquad (17)$$

The interesting phenomena that's revealed is, the *pcp* appear to bond in quantized ratios! And the affect is stronger among all the primes $< n$ versus just those $< n/2$. So as the primes density decreases as n grows, the bonding between all the possible $p_r < n$ is slightly stronger|larger than just for those $< n/2$.

The n values in Table 1. only end in '0', so the table below shows results for larger consecutive even n that end in each even digit, and have the same number of $\pi(n)$ primes for those values.

n	$\varphi(n)/2$	$\pi(n)$	PCP	% PCP	First Prime Pair	Last Prime Pair
900,000,000	120,000,000	46,009,215	4,132,595	17.96	[37, 899999963]	[449999993, 450000007]
900,000,002	204,211,920	46,009,215	1,724,113	7.49	[73, 899999929]	[449999981, 450000121]
900,000,004	224,969,472	46,009,215	1,550,567	6.74	[41, 899999963]	[449999887, 450000117]
900,000,006	150,000,000	46,009,215	3,099,095	13.47	[43, 899999963]	[449999783, 450000223]
900,000,008	224,956,800	46,009,215	1,550,273	6.74	[79, 899999929]	[449999731, 450000277]

Table 1a.

We still see this quantizing phenomena, and that the largest number of *pcp* for n have the highest ratios. Now that it's been revealed, hopefully more research will be pursued to study and characterize it.

What is seen here is a deterministic pattern in the primes distribution, that facilitates they form prime pairs in such numbers, and in such ratios. This would not be possible if the primes existed randomly. Thus the data also illustrates again from this property, ***the primes do not exist randomly!***

Empirical Data Table 2.

Here we see the *lhr* data variance in the region bounded by $r_{max}+2$. While r_{max} linearly increases with n , the number of residues and *pcp* prime pairs is still predominantly a function of the factorization of n .

n	$r_{max} + 2$	$lhr(r_{max+})$	$\pi(r_{max+})$	$PCP(r_{max+})$	% $PCP(r_{max+})$	First Prime Pair	Last Prime Pair(r_{max+})
1,000,000	1,001	400	168	20	11.90	[17, 999983]	[977, 999023]
2,000,000	1,416	565	223	24	10.76	[7, 1999993]	[1321, 1998679]
3,000,000	1,734	462	270	63	23.33	[43, 2999957]	[1721, 2998279]
4,000,000	2,001	800	303	34	11.22	[29, 3999971]	[1997, 3998003]
5,000,000	2,238	894	332	39	11.75	[37, 4999963]	[2113, 4997887]
6,000,000	2,451	653	363	84	23.14	[7, 5999993]	[2447, 5997553]
7,000,000	2,647	907	383	54	14.09	[3, 6999997]	[2621, 6997379]
8,000,000	2,830	1,131	410	45	10.98	[7, 7999993]	[2797, 7997203]
9,000,000	3,001	800	431	96	22.27	[7, 8999993]	[2917, 8997083]
10,000,000	3,164	1,265	447	44	9.84	[29, 9999971]	[2633, 9997367]
11,000,000	3,318	1,205	466	51	10.94	[3, 10999997]	[3271, 10996729]
12,000,000	3,466	923	485	100	10.62	[11, 11999989]	[3461, 11996539]
13,000,000	3,607	1,331	504	68	13.39	[3, 12999997]	[3461, 12996539]
14,000,000	3,743	1,283	522	82	15.71	[19, 13999981]	[3739, 13996261]
15,000,000	3,874	1,032	536	111	20.71	[19, 14999981]	[3847, 14996153]
16,000,000	4,001	1,600	551	61	11.07	[11, 15999989]	[3989, 15996011]
17,000,000	4,125	1,552	566	68	12.01	[37, 16999963]	[4093, 16995907]
18,000,000	4,244	1,131	582	112	19.24	[13, 17999987]	[4241, 17995759]
19,000,000	4,360	1,651	595	66	11.09	[3, 18999997]	[4271, 18995729]
20,000,000	4,474	1,789	607	62	10.21	[19, 19999981]	[4363, 19995637]
21,000,000	4,584	1,047	620	141	22.74	[23, 20999977]	[4561, 20995439]
22,000,000	4,692	1,706	634	70	11.04	[23, 21999977]	[4547, 21995453]
23,000,000	4,797	1,835	645	63	9.77	[7, 22999993]	[4723, 22995277]
24,000,000	4,900	1,305	654	129	19.72	[19, 23999981]	[4703, 23995297]
25,000,000	5,001	2,000	669	71	10.61	[17, 24999983]	[4889, 24995111]
26,000,000	5,101	1,883	682	76	11.14	[67, 25999933]	[4999, 25995001]
27,000,000	5,198	1,385	692	153	22.11	[19, 26999981]	[5171, 26994829]
28,000,000	5,293	1,815	701	91	12.98	[101, 27999899]	[5279, 27994721]
29,000,000	5,387	2,080	710	75	10.56	[61, 28999939]	[5347, 28994653]
30,000,000	5,479	1,461	724	148	20.44	[11, 29999989]	[5443, 29994557]
31,000,000	5,569	2,155	735	83	11.29	[11, 30999989]	[5501, 30994499]
32,000,000	5,658	2,262	745	73	9.79	[61, 31999939]	[5647, 31994353]
33,000,000	5,746	1,392	756	173	22.88	[17, 32999983]	[5693, 32994307]
34,000,000	5,832	2,194	765	85	11.11	[107, 33999893]	[5813, 33994187]
35,000,000	5,918	2,028	777	81	10.42	[31, 34999969]	[5791, 34994209]

Table 2.

The Tale of Table 2.

Here % PCP(r_{max+}) = $(pcp / \pi(r_{max+})) \cdot 100$ is the percentage of primes as $pcp \leq r_{max}+2$, and other parameters r_{max+} for $lhr \leq r_{max}+2$. The % PCP values for n in both tables closely match, though the bounded regions become a smaller percentage of $n/2$ as n grows. As a ratio of $n/2$ it's essentially, $n^{1/2}/n/2 = 2/n^{1/2}$. So as n increases it's a decreasing percentage, and many more pcp occur outside the region than in it. But the bounded pcp still relatively increase because the regions increase in absolute size. So for $n = 1,000,000$ its bounded region ratio is $2/1000$, or 0.2%, and 20 of its total of 5402 pcp (0.37%) come from it.

This is fast|memory efficient Crystal code to generate the bounded region data for r_{max} given in Table 2.

```
# Compile: $ crystal build --release --mcpu native prime_pairs_rmax.cr
# Run as:  $ ./prime_pairs_rmax 10_000_000_000

require "./prime-utils.cr" # provides method: prime?

def prime_pairs_rmax(n) # generate rmax bounded pcp for even n > 6
  return puts "Input not even n > 6" unless n.even? && n > 6

  lhr_rmax = Math.isqrt(n-2) + 2 # the rmax + 2 high bound
  lhr = 3u64.step(to: lhr_rmax, by: 2).select { |r| r if r.gcd(n) == 1 }.to_a # gen bounded lhr

  pcp_rmax = lhr.select { |r| r if r.prime? && (n-r).prime? }.to_a # identify bounded lhr pcp
  (puts "no pcp in bound for #{n}\n"; return) if pcp_rmax.empty? # if no pcp, report n value

  pp [n, lhr_rmax, lhr.size, pcp_rmax.size] # show n, lhr_rmax, lhr count, pcp count
  pp [pcp_rmax.first, n-pcp_rmax.first] # show first pcp prime pair of n
  pp [pcp_rmax.last, n-pcp_rmax.last] # show last pcp prime pair <= rmax + 2
end

n = (ARGV[0].to_u64 underscore: true) # get n input from terminal
t1 = Time.monotonic # start execution timing
prime_pairs_rmax(n) # execute code
pp Time.monotonic - t1 # show execution time
```

```
$ ./prime_pairs_rmax 123_456_780 [123456780, 11113, 2900, 268]
[19, 123456761]
[11113, 123445667]
00:00:00.000434230

$ ./primes_pair_rmax 1_234_567_809_876_542 [1234567809876542, 35136419, 17540241, 82032]
[61, 1234567809876481]
[35136133, 1234567774740409]
00:00:02.530332120
```

PCP Bounds Asymptotic Behavior

As with the *PGT's Postulate* bounds, we are concerned with the asymptotic behavior of the *pcp* bounds. This Crystal code was used to test the *pcp* bounds adherence over ranges of even values. It verified for every n up to 10^{12} (1,000,000,000,000), and for at least the first 100M (100,000,000) from $10^{13}..10^{19}$, that a *pcp* prime pairs comes from each bounded region, except for 49 small values. Each of these has primes in their bounded regions, but they don't form *pcp* prime pairs. All the *pcp* prime pairs for them come from outside the bounded region defined by r_{max} . Here are their values:

98, 122, 220, 308, 346, 488, 556, 962, 992, 1144, 1150, 1354, 1360, 1362, 1408, 1424, 1532, 1768, 1928, 2078, 2438, 2512, 2530, 2618, 2642, 3458, 3818, 3848, 4618, 4886, 5978, 6008, 7426, 9596, 9602, 11438, 11642, 12886, 13148, 13562, 14198, 14678, 16502, 18908, 21368, 23426, 23456, 43532, 63274

Because the factorization of n is plays the most prominent role in the distribution of the *pcp*, small values of n show the most variance within the bounded regions. As the square root of n increases with n , the bounded regions become larger in absolute value, and the affects of factorization become more normalized over both halves residues of n , ensuring *pcp* prime residues exist in the bounded regions.

Thus as n increases the regions bounded by r_{max} increase, and from the less strict *PGTP* bounds we know they always contain primes, and these will form *pcp* prime pairs. Thus from these regions alone, we "know" there exist prime pairs for all increasing n , establishing its asymptotic behavior as $n \rightarrow \infty$, and thus the validity of *Goldbach's Conjecture* for all even n .

```
require "./prime-utils.cr"           # provides methods: prime? | next_prime

def prime_pairs_rmax_check(n)        # check at least one pcp residue within bounds for n
  p, lhr_rmax = 2u64, Math.isqrt(n-2) + 2 # the rmax + 2 high bound
  while (p = p.next_prime) <= lhr_rmax; return if (n-p).prime? end
  puts "no pcp in bound for #{n}\n"    # no pcp residue, report n value
end

n1 = (ARGV[0].to_u64 underscore: true) # inputs taken as u64 values up to 1.8 x 10^19 (2^64)
n2 = (ARGV[1].to_u64 underscore: true) # change to u128 for values up to 3.4 x 10^38 (2^128)

t1 = Time.monotonic                  # start execution timing
n1.step(to: n2, by: 2) do |n|        # for even n values in range
  prime_pairs_rmax_check(n)          # check for n if a pcp residue in bounded region
  print "\rchecked up to #{n.format}" if n.divisible_by?(100_000) # output for every 100K done
end
puts "\nTested Values #{n1.format} to #{n2.format}"
puts Time.monotonic - t1              # show execution time
```

```
$ ./prime_pairs_rmax_check 8 500    $ ./prime_pairs_rmax_check 65_000 100_000_000
no pcp in bound for 98              checked up to 100,000,000
no pcp in bound for 122             Tested Values 65,000 to 100,000,000
no pcp in bound for 128             00:00:55.456560943
no pcp in bound for 220
no pcp in bound for 308
no pcp in bound for 346
no pcp in bound for 488
Tested Values 8 to 500
00:00:00.000150531
```

Below is the Crystal source code for prime-utils.cr.

```

require "big"

@[Link("gmp")]
lib LibGMP
  fun mpz_powm = __gmpz_powm(rop : MPZ*, base : MPZ*, exp : MPZ*, mod : MPZ*)
end

def powmodgmp(b, e, m)
  y = BigInt.new; LibGMP.mpz_powm(y, b.to_big_i, e.to_big_i, m.to_big_i)
  y
end

def powmodint(b, e, m)
  r = typeof(m).new(1);
  b = b % m; b = typeof(m).new(b)
  while e > 0; r = (r &* b) % m if e.odd?; e >>= 1; b = (b &* b) % m end
  r
end

def powmod(b, e, m); m > UInt32::MAX ? powmodgmp(b, e, m) : powmodint(b, e, m.to_u64) end

struct Int
  def next_prime # return the next prime number > self
    n = self
    return (n >> 1) + 2 if n <= 2 # to do 2 or 3
    n = n &+ 1 | 1 # 1st odd number > n
    until (res = n % 6) & 0b11 == 1; n &+= 2 end # n first P3 pc >= n, w/residue 1 or 5
    inc = (res == 1) ? 4 : 2 # set its P3 PGS value, inc by 2 and 4
    until n.prime?; n &+= inc; inc ^= 0b110; end # find first prime P3 pc
    n
  end

  # PGT and Miller-Rabin combined primality tests
  def prime? (k = 5) # set k higher for more primer? reliability
    # Use PGT residue checks for small values < PRIMES.last**2
    return PRIMES.includes? self if self <= PRIMES.last
    return false if MODPN.gcd(self) != 1
    return true if self < PRIMES.last &** 2
    primemr?(k)
  end

  def primemr? (k = 5) # deterministic Miller-Rabin w/witnesses
    neg_one_mod = n = d = self - 1 # these are even as self is always odd
    d >>= d.trailing_zeros_count # shift out factors of 2 to make d odd
    # wits = [range, [wit_prms]] or nil
    wits = WITNESS_RANGES.find { |range, wits| range > self }
    witnesses = wits ? wits[1] : k.times.map{ rand(self - 4) + 2 }
    witnesses.each do |b|
      next if b.divisible_by? self # skip base if multiple of input: (b % self) == 0
      y = powmod(b, d, self) # y = (b**d) mod self
      s = d
      until y == 1 || y == neg_one_mod || s == n
        y = (y &* y) % self # y = (y**2) mod self
        s <<= 1
      end
      return false unless y == neg_one_mod || s.odd?
    end
    true
  end
end

private MODPN = 232862364358497360900063316880507363070u128.to_big_i # 101# is largest for u128
private PRIMES = [2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, 37, 41, 43, 47, 53, 59, 61, 67, 71, 73, 79, 83, 89, 97, 101, 103]

# Best known deterministic witnesses for given range and set of bases
# https://miller-rabin.appspot.com/
private WITNESS_RANGES = {
  341_531u64 => [9345883071009581737u64],
  1_050_535_501u64 => [336781006125u64, 9639812373923155u64],
  350_269_456_337u64 => [4230279247111683200u64, 14694767155120705706u64, 16641139526367750375u64],
  55_245_642_489_451u64 => [2u64, 141889084524735u64, 1199124725622454117u64, 11096072698276303650u64],
  7_999_252_175_582_851u64 => [2u64, 4130806001517u64, 149795463772692060u64, 186635894390467037u64,
    3967304179347715805u64],
  585_226_005_592_931_977u64 => [2u64, 123635709730000u64, 9233062284813009u64, 43835965440333360u64,
    761179012939631437u64, 1263739024124850375u64],
  18_446_744_073_709_551_615u64 => [2, 325, 9375, 28178, 450775, 9780504, 1795265022] of UInt64
}
end

```

The Epistemology of Math

A key question this paper raises, implicitly if not explicitly, is how do we “know” something? That is, what constitutes the establishment of mathematical knowledge? In math there is invariably more than one way to “know” things (solve problems). And usually, the simplest way to understand something is the preferred way to explain it.

In this paper I use a field of math I call *Prime Generator Theory*. It uses centuries old knowledge of basic modular arithmetic, and the math and properties of residues of multiplicative modular groups. At the foundational arithmetic level nothing is new here. However at the conceptual level, *PGT* opens up an understanding of the primes heretofore not imagined. And it's at this conceptual level we are able to “know” things about the primes, in simple ways, and without the need for complex computations.

Picking the right model to frame a problem is essential to its understanding. *Fermat's Last Theory* (1637) stood unsolved until 1994, when Andrew Wiles used elliptic curves and modular forms as the framework to understand and solve it. Here, using modular groups make *Goldbach's Conjecture* simple to understand and solve, and also significantly improve upon *Bertrand's Postulate* (1845). I previously used *PGT* to prove *Polignac's Conjecture*, more commonly known as the *Twin Primes Conjecture* [2].

One key understanding that *PGT* provides is that ***the primes do not exist randomly*** among the integers. They exist as the congruent modular values of the residues of modular groups \mathbb{Z}_n , which means ***there is a deterministic order to the primes***. Thus it is unnecessary (even counter productive) to model their distribution as random, and then employ the computational tools used for those models as a way to understand them. Thus the *GC* stood from 1742 until now (2025) “unsolved” using those techniques.

A defining property of a valid theory is it can predict empirically testable results. *PGT* provides not only the mathematical basis to establish *Goldbach's Conjecture*, et al, but also the means to “know” how many primes pairs exist for any even n , and their exact values, using simple algorithms/software.

Another key, and modern, way to mathematically “know” things now is by computer modeling. This has become an essential, and indispensable, tool for computational analysis in so many fields now. Here, the empirical data substantiates both the paper's establishment of *Goldbach Conjecture* as true, but also *PGT's Postulate* being a better, more precise, bound on p than given by *Bertrand's Postulate*.

Thus marrying better theory, with better computational tools to test them, can lead to better progress in solving age old problems (and not just in math). But it's the *imagination* to derive better theories that is tantamount to the advancement of knowledge (of “knowing”). We must be willing (and attempt) to see things with new eyes, or more accurately, process the things we see with a different consciousness of the possibilities of “knowing” them.

Because there is an “art” to knowing. It doesn't always flow from the linear progression of small dots being connected to draw a picture of a larger whole (truth). Sometimes (many times) it is one person making a leap in imagination to see a problem in a way not envisioned before. And usually this means the complexity and confusion of old thinking gets wiped away, and replaced with an insight that makes things so much simpler to know and understand. And as Einstein said – *Imagination is more important than knowledge*.

Conclusion

Prime Generator Theory (PGT) provides the most powerful and conceptually simple mathematical framework for understanding the nature, characteristics, and distribution of the primes. By treating even values of n as modular groups \mathbb{Z}_n , we apply the properties of residues to easily identify the prime pairs of n , which deterministically exist as the *modular complement pairs (mcp)* of strictly primes, i.e. they exist as the *prime complement pair (pcp)* residues of \mathbb{Z}_n .

From this framework we establish every even integer $n > 6$ will (must) have at least one *pcp* prime pair. The properties of this framework can then be algorithmically constructed to identify all the *pcp* prime pairs. This simple algorithm is then translated into software that provides the total count of *pcp* prime pairs of n , and displays their values as desired. This is done without the need to perform any explicit prime searches or tests. The structure of the \mathbb{Z}_n residues guarantees identification of the primes.

We also see *Bertrand's Postulate* is just a necessary condition that falls out of the modular symmetry of the *pcp*. There always must be a prime in the intervals $n/2 < p < n$ in order for there to be prime pairs. As an extra bonus, we're able to create much smaller (tighter) dynamically adjusting bounds for p , compared to the wider static *BP* bounds, which become relatively larger as n increases. Thus we now have a much better understanding of the distribution of the primes.

Finally, empirical data is provided for an increasing range of n values, showing their total *pcp* counts, and their first and last prime pairs values. It shows large variances in the *pcp* counts for close n values, as a functions of their factorization profiles. We also see the ratios of the *pcp* primes as a percentage of all the primes $< n$ occur in quantized bands. Thus the *pcp* increase as n does, verifying that *Goldbach's Conjecture* is correct, but also revealing so much more to the story than was previously known.

References

- [1] Oliveiria e Silva, Herzog, and Pardi – Empirical Verification Of The Even Goldbach Conjecture And Computation Of Prime Gaps Up To $4 \cdot 10^{18}$, Journal: Math. Comp. **83** (2014), 2033-2060.
<https://www.ams.org/journals/mcom/2014-83-288/S0025-5718-2013-02787-1/S0025-5718-2013-02787-1.pdf>
- [2] Jabari Zakiya – On The Infinity of Twin Primes and other K-tuples, International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research (IJMCR), Vol 13 No 1 (2025), 4739-4761.
<https://ijmcr.in/index.php/ijmcr/article/view/867/678> (pdf)
- [3] Jabari Zakiya – Twin Primes Segmented Sieve of Zakiya (SSoZ) Explained, J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res 2(2), 119 - 147, 2023.
<https://www.opastpublishers.com/open-access-articles/twin-primes-segmented-sieve-of-zakiya-ssoz-explained.pdf>